

'Disciplined Reactions' using Phenyl Isothiocyanate as a Cyclocondensing Agent. A Novel One-flask Synthesis of 2-Substituted-4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-1-phenyl-2-imidazolin-5-ones

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Phenyl isothiocyanate mediated condensation of *N*-acetyl- and *N*-*p*-toluoylglycines with vanillin gives 2-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxystyryl- and 2-*p*-toluyl-4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-1-phenyl-2-imidazolin-5-ones, respectively.

CONSTRUCTION of a somewhat complex organic molecule generally involves several steps. In some cases, the steps can be telescoped and the synthesis can be accomplished in one flask. These and similar ordered transformations designed to give a desired product can be called 'disciplined reactions'. This concept is illustrated in this communication by the synthesis of the title compounds.

1,2-Disubstituted-4-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-imidazolin-5-ones (**1a**) were implicated as the chromophore responsible for fluorescence of the green fluorescent protein of *Aequorea* and *Renilla*, and their synthesis involved a circuitous route¹. In our approach to construct a similar system, we heated *N*-acetylglycine (**2a**) with phenyl isothiocyanate at 160–70° for 30 min in the presence of vanillin, using pyridine as a catalyst. The product was characterised as 4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxystyryl-1-phenyl-2-imidazolin-5-one (**1b**). It was found that the yield of **1b** increased on increasing the molar ratio of vanillin.

- a ; R¹=Me or Ph, R²=H, R³=Me,
R⁴=CH₂COOEt, R⁵=H
b ; R¹=H, R²=*m*-MeO, *p*-HOC₆H₄,
R³=H, R⁴=Ph, R⁵=MeO

A similar attempt to condense *p*-toluoylglycine (**2b**) with phenyl isothiocyanate in the presence of vanillin led to the formation of a mixture from which 4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-*p*-toluyl-1-phenyl-2-imidazolin-5-one (**6b**) was isolated as the main product. Also, small amounts of 4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-*p*-toluyl-2-oxazolin-5-one (**4b**) and 2-*N*-*p*-toluoylamino-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxycinnamanilide (**5b**) were obtained in this reaction. Compound **5b** underwent cyclisation to **6b** on heating at an elevated temperature or in glacial acetic acid in the presence of freshly fused sodium acetate.

The interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate and an *N*-acylglycine would produce 2-substituted-2-oxazolin-5-one (**3**) and aniline, both of which would compete for condensation with vanillin when it is present in the reaction mixture. Compound **3** undergoes facile aminolysis, but in the present case *N*-acylglycylanilines (RCONHCH₂-CONHPh) were not discernible, which could be best explained by the assumption that the liberated aniline was converted into vanillin anil, the latter then participated in the condensation with **3** to give 2-substituted-4-*m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-oxazolin-5-one (**4**) and aniline which, in turn, underwent subsequent changes. This mechanism is substantiated by the isolation of **4** and **5** which were prepared by an unambiguous route^{2,3}. It is noteworthy that the methyl group of **6** was found to be active which accounts for the formation of **1b**. In contrast, the methyl group of the *p*-toluyl substituent in **6b** was inactive and it failed to undergo condensation with an aromatic aldehyde under the present reaction conditions. In the present set of transformations, phenyl isothiocyanate played the role of a counter-attack reagent⁴, and all the steps proceeded in a disciplined manner, thereby providing a one-flask synthesis of the target molecule.

Products were characterised by spectral data and elemental analyses.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir (nujol) and ¹H nmr (CDCl₃ with TMS as internal standard) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 720, JEOL FX-90Q and/or Varian FT 80 spectrometers, respectively. Elemental analyses were carried out by a Coleman analyser.

Compound 1b: A mixture of *N*-acetylglycine, phenyl isothiocyanate, and vanillin, taken in the ratio of 1:1.2:2 respectively, was heated for 30 min at 160–70° with pyridine as a catalyst. The residue was washed with light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°), sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and the products were separated by fractional crystallisation from benzene and/or ethanol, (41%), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 69.21; H, 5.63; N, 5.92. C₂₆H₂₂N₂O₅·1/2H₂O requires: C, 69.18; H, 5.09; N, 6.20%); ν_{max} 3 250 and 3 150 (OH), 1 710 (CO), 1 660 and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.80

(3H, s, OCH₃), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.30 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, ArCH=CH), 6.75–7.75 (14H two exchangeable, m, 11×Ar-H, =CH, and 2×Ar-OH) and 7.90 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz, ArCH=CH).

Compound 4b: It was prepared by the procedure previously reported² and recrystallised from ethanol, (35%), m.p. 172–73° (Found: C, 69.72; H, 5.01; N, 4.71. C₁₈H₁₅NO₄ requires: C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53%); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH), 1 780, 1 770 (azlactone) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ(CDCl₃) 2.41 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.14 (1H, s, exchangeable, ArOH) and 6.87–8.87 (8H, m, ArH and =CH).

Compound 5b: It was prepared by the procedure previously reported³ and recrystallised from ethanol, (33%), m.p. 200° (Found: C, 71.21; H, 5.62; N, 6.73. C₂₄H₂₂N₂O₄ requires: C, 71.64; H, 5.47; N, 6.96%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 320 (OH), 3 290 and 3 200 (NH), 1 660 cm⁻¹ (CO and C=C). Because of insufficient solubility, its ¹H nmr spectrum could not be recorded.

Compound 6b: The procedure is same as given under compound 1b. The yield (48%), m.p. 230°

(Found : C, 71.21 ; H, 5.35 ; N, 6.92. $C_{24}H_{20}N_2O_3$. H_2O requires : C, 71.64 ; H, 5.47 ; N, 6.96%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 400, 3 200 (OH), 1 720 (CO), 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=C) ; $\delta(CDCl_3)$ 2.31 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 3.26 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.81 (1H, s, exchangeable, $ArOH$) and 6.74–7.94 (13H, m, $12 \times ArH$ and =CH).

References

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